

Shreevaishnavas

also known as "Sri Vaishnavas"

By

Entry tags: Indic Religious Traditions, Religious Group

The Shreevaishnavas are a community of devotees and worshipers brought together by the medieval saint, Ramanuja. They worship the deity Vishnu and his various forms. The roots for the community's philosophical understandings can be traced back to the Vedas and the Pancha ratra texts. The word Alwar means 'one who rules.' The devotional compositions of the Alwars are compiled in the Nalayira Divya Prabandham (4000 divine verses). The names of the Alwars are as follows: Poigai, Bhutha, Pey, Thondaradi, Mathurakavi, Peria, Andal, Kulasekhara, Namm, Tirupana, Thirumazhisai and Tirumangai. The Alwars practiced fervent devotion and were able to perform miracles as a result. They belonged to the elite as well as the Kshatriya and other "lower castes." A number of the Alwars shared an informal relationship, i.e., a relationship of love and understanding with the deity, Vishnu. In the verses of the Alwars, we see longing or viraha bhakti as well as a wide range of other emotions. The work of the Alwars is known as the Tamil Veda. For the Alwars, the grace of the deities are available naturally without specific efforts on the part of the devotees--this later becomes a point of contention leading to a break in the Srivaishnava community, who are Vishnu and his consort's Lakshmi's worshipers and followers of the Alwars. The modern community of Srivaishnavas, also known as Iyengars. Subsequent acharyas have shaped this Vaishnava sect. Important among them are Ramanuja, Vedanta Desika and Pillai Lokacharya. Ramanuja's philosophy of Vishistadvaita synthesizes diverse philosophies and offers a mode of harmonious devotion to followers. The legacy of the Alwars is alive in the Srivaishnava community to this day.

Date Range: 500 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Tamil Nadu and Karnataka, India

Region tags: Bhakti, Hinduism

All the Tamil-speaking regions of medieval India, the current state of Tamil Nadu and parts of another state called Karnataka.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)